

1 **Advances in Remote Sensing and Machine Learning for Land Use/Land**
2 **Cover Change Detection and Climate Model Bias Correction: Methods and**
3 **Applications**

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13 **ABSTRACT**

14 Ecosystems globally are increasingly threatened by the integrated impacts of human activities and climate change,
15 especially in the Ethiopian Rift Valley, where data are scarce. Therefore, there is an urgent need for implementing
16 advances in sustainable resource management. This study presented a systematic meta-analysis that synthesized
17 more than 100 peer-reviewed studies (2004-2025) to critically evaluate how remote sensing (RS) and machine
18 learning (ML) could be integrated for detecting LULC change and climate model bias. Using a PRISMA protocol,
19 the methodological progression from traditional statistical approaches was evaluated through advanced deep-
20 learning and hybrid methods. The results provided strong evidence that integrating RS and ML had significant
21 transformative potential; however, there still remained a "gap" in their integration. Both fields advanced greatly, yet
22 each existed as a largely independent entity. Recent studies addressed this disintegration, however operational
23 frameworks were scarce. In order to close this gap, a novel integrated conceptual framework was proposed. This
24 would dynamically integrate multi-sensor data fusion, ML-based LULC mapping, hybrid ML-statistical bias
25 correction, and SWAT+ hydrological models into a single end-to-end processing pipeline designed specifically for
26 basins that contained little or no data. Transfer learning and explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) could be used to
27 solve the problem of applying data-hungry models in situations where very little or no data were available. The
28 integration of XAI methods such as SHAP and LIME gave a promise for improving model interpretability in
29 environmental applications. The review suggests that robust-policy-relevant environmental prediction depended on
30 designing combined systems that were not only accurate but also interpretable and adaptable to local conditions.

31 **Keywords:** Climate Model Bias Correction, Data Integration, Land Cover Change Detection, Machine Learning,
32 Remote Sensing, Explainable AI

33 **1. INTRODUCTION**

34 Accurate land use/land cover change detection is a critical component in monitoring the
35 environment, evaluating the health of the ecosystems, and managing resources sustainably in
36 fragile ecosystems in the Ethiopian Rift Valley (Ayalew, 2023; Degife et al., 2019; Tolessa et al.,
37 2017). The availability of open-access satellite archives (for example, Landsat) transformed our
38 ability to perform long-term, global monitoring of environmental change (Cohen & Goward,
39 2004; Wulder et al., 2019). Moreover, the emergence of harmonized Landsat-Sentinel products
40 created new opportunities for high-frequency monitoring at moderate spatial resolutions
41 (Claverie et al., 2018; Meresa et al., 2023). The fragile ecosystems of the Ethiopian Rift Valley's
42 particularly the area around the Ziway Shala Sub-Basin are currently experiencing the combined
43 effects of climate variability and land use/land cover change, which negatively impacted these
44 ecosystems (Ayalew, 2023; Belete et al., 2017; Blenkinsop & Smith, 2007; Truneh et al., 2024;
45 Wondrade et al., 2014). Recent assessments showed increasing rates of land degradation and lake
46 level decline, with profound implications for food security and livelihoods (Berihun et al., 2023;
47 Getaneh et al., 2024). Climate variability and land-use change affected lake levels, river flows,
48 and hydrological changes. This might negatively impact water security, biodiversity, and the
49 livelihoods of millions of people who lived within this basin (Ayenew & Legesse, 2007; Hailu,
50 2019; Legesse et al., 2004; Mulu et al., 2024). Proper evaluation of these impacts was necessary
51 for the continued use of the resources, but this was constrained by methodological approaches
52 and lack of data (Donauer et al., 2020; Mersha et al., 2023).

53 Remote Sensing has long provided the basis for environmental monitoring by delivering spatially
54 homogeneous, multi-date measurements of the surface of the Earth. The long archive of missions
55 like Landsat and the high temporal resolution of Sentinel constellations provided unique benefits
56 for long-term land use/land cover change monitoring (Drusch et al., 2012). The combination of
57 radar (SAR) data further improved monitoring capabilities, particularly in cloud-prone tropical
58 regions (Flores, Anderson et al., 2019; Pham-Duc et al., 2023). The advancement of continuous
59 change detection algorithms, capable of leveraging the entire Landsat archive, has been
60 particularly transformative for detecting land surface dynamics (Zhu & Woodcock, 2014;

61 Hansen et al., 2013). For instance, Landsat time-series have shown a marked decline in the size
62 of Lake Abijata and changes in Lake Ziway, because of climatic variation and anthropogenic
63 water abstractions (Hailu, 2019; Wulder et al., 2019). On the other hand, climate models
64 (GCMs/RCMs) were fundamental in predicting future scenarios but were influenced by
65 systematic biases that distorted local precipitation and temperature patterns, yielding doubtful
66 impact evaluations (Blenkinsop & Smith, 2007; Brienen et al., 2010; Fowler et al., 2007; Meresa
67 et al., 2023; Senatore et al., 2022). In data-poor areas, such biases must be corrected to achieve
68 quality climate change impact modeling (Cannon et al., 2015; Hempel et al., 2013; Teutschbein
69 & Seibert, 2012). Recent intercomparison studies underlined the relative advantages of different
70 bias correction methods for East African applications (Gebrechorkos et al., 2019; Wubneh et al.,
71 2022).

72 The parallel emergence of ML has revolutionized both fields. For land use/land cover
73 classification, ML algorithms like Random Forest (RF) and Convolutional Neural Networks
74 (CNNs) have consistently outperformed traditional models (Belgiu & Drăgu, 2016; Maxwell et
75 al., 2018). The advent of vision transformers and attention mechanisms has further improved the
76 state-of-the-art in satellite image analysis (Dosovitskiy et al., 2021). For climate studies, ML-
77 based bias correction schemes have demonstrated higher skill in capturing non-linear bias
78 patterns than classical statistical schemes like Quantile Mapping (Vandal et al., 2019; Wang &
79 Tian, 2022). Deep learning approaches, mainly convolutional and recurrent architectures, have
80 revealed remarkable skill in downscaling precipitation fields (Wu et al., 2024; Zhong et al.,
81 2025). The development of a combined use of remote sensing and an approach to apply ML
82 techniques for climate bias correction had greater abilities to manage and monitor the
83 environment. They had the capabilities to provide near real-time monitoring and prediction of the
84 change in lake surface area, allow the investigation of the relationship of rainfall to water
85 resources, and provide collaborative decision-making tools to assist with sustainable governance
86 of irrigation systems. Furthermore, integrating remotely sensed land cover transformation data
87 with bias-corrected climatic data in a hydrologic model such as SWAT+ presented a unique
88 capacity to capture the cumulative effects of climate change and human activities on surface
89 waters (Ayalew et al., 2022). In data-scarce African basins, recent SWAT+ applications
90 demonstrated the value of coupling satellite-based products for model calibration (Wagner et al.,
91 2023).

92 However, a careful review revealed that these advances primarily progressed in isolation. While
93 research concentrated on refining either change detection using RS or climate bias correction,
94 their combination remained underdeveloped (Ehret et al., 2012; Haile et al., 2020). This isolation
95 impacted the operational comprehension and holistic prediction of environmental responses. This
96 review therefore argued that the future challenge would not require the further refinement of
97 these domains in isolation but their intentional combination. This review aimed to integrate the
98 most recent remote sensing and ML methods for land use/land cover change detection and
99 climate model bias correction, identify major methodological challenges and opportunities,
100 critically evaluate the advantages and shortcomings of existing methods, and propose a
101 synthesized, integrated framework for holistic environmental forecasting to guide future
102 research. The contributions of this review would be: (1) a systematic review and identification of
103 the "integration gap" between RS/ ML for land use/land cover change and climate science. (2)
104 proposal of a distinctly new conceptual framework that would synthesizes these disparate fields
105 into an actionable research agenda specifically intended for data-sparse regions.

106

107 **2. METHODS**

108 A comprehensive review of the technological innovations in Remote-Sensing (RS) and Machine
109 Learning (ML) for detecting LULC changes and correcting biases in climate models was
110 accomplished through a systematic and critical analysis methodology. The objective was to
111 create a clear method for identifying trends, missing areas in research on how emerging
112 technologies may be integrated into other datasets. The objective was achieved through a
113 systematic approach with four steps: (1) conducting a systematic literature review; (2) screening
114 the literature to identify those studies that met the eligibility requirements; (3) extracting and
115 synthesizing the data using a structured approach; and (4) generating an integrated view of the
116 findings..

117 **2.1 Literature Search and Selection Strategy**

118 This systematic literature review underwent a structured and reproducible methodological
119 process to identify, evaluate, and synthesize research on land use/land cover change detection

120 and climate model bias correction and its implication for Lake Hydrology. The process began
121 with the systematic identification of relevant studies utilizing major scientific databases, such as
122 Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore, and Google Scholar, MDPI Remote Sensing, Elsevier
123 journals. It also used search terms associated with hydrology, Remote Sensing (RS), Machine
124 Learning (ML), land use/land cover , change detection, GCMs/RCMs, downscaling, rift
125 valley/scarce regions and bias correction. The updated PRISMA 2020 guidelines were used for
126 systematic reviews (Page et al., 2021). The PRISMA protocol was used to ensure a systematic
127 and reproducible literature retrieval process allowing for transparent reporting of results. This
128 systematic approach included limiting source materials to peer-reviewed articles, conference
129 proceedings, and book chapters mostly published from 2004 through 2025 to reflect the current
130 development of ML within these areas. The literature search produced an initial set of 285
131 records. After an initial scoping review, the search was expanded to include foundational
132 methodological papers from additional geographical regions, resulting in a total of over 100
133 peer-reviewed studies that were combined and cleaned to eliminate duplicates. In addition to
134 database searches, 20 records were identified through "snowballing" (manual searching of
135 reference lists of key review articles) and forward citation tracking.

136 **2.2 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria**

137 The inclusion criteria for the studies were based on (1) the development or application of new
138 method to detect land use/land cover (LULC) changes or a climate model bias correction using
139 RS/ML, (2) an assessment of model performance (accuracy, RMSE, skill score) (Fraser &
140 Congalton, 2019), and (3) a discussion of challenges, limitations, or future directions for
141 developing integrated applications of RS/ML. Studies employing advanced validation strategies,
142 together with spatial cross-validation to avoid overfitting, were emphasized (Meyer & Pebesma,
143 2022; Milà et al., 2024). Studies focusing purely on non-terrestrial applications, non-
144 hydrological aspects of climate science like oceanography or those without a strong
145 methodological advancement or application were excluded. Studies that had no applied aspects
146 to them (theoretical only), conducted in non-terrestrial environments, or reported not in English
147 were excluded.

148 **2.3 Data Extraction and Synthesis**

149 A review of each selected study was completed using a standardized database for storing key
150 data about each study. The data included a) research objective(s) and geographical coverage; b)
151 remote sensing data and ML algorithms (Kuhn & Johnson, 2013) used in combination including:
152 Landsat, Sentinel, MODIS remote sensing data sets, and random forest, convolutional neural
153 networks, support vector machines, long-short-term memory networks, and artificial neural
154 networks ML algorithms; c) methods of detecting or correcting change; d) performance metrics
155 presented; e) weaknesses and strength of the methodology (Simpson, 2018). The extracted data
156 were then synthesized thematically to provide an understanding of the evolution of
157 methodologies, enable comparison of performance, and identify challenges that continue to exist
158 and research gaps. This thematic synthesis process, which we refer to as "thematic organization,"
159 systematically involved categorizing findings by methodological approach to compare studies
160 with different objectives and geographical context. Finally, the strengths and weaknesses of
161 existing methods were critically analyzed. And the case for integrating these methods into more
162 effective framework was articulated

163 **2.4. Framework Integration**

164 In the final stage of the methodology, the findings were synthesized into a hybrid RS-ML
165 conceptual framework, intended for semi-arid and data limited freshwater basin. Attempts were
166 made to focus on transparency, traceability, and adherence to accepted environmental monitoring
167 best practices and data-driven ecosystem assessment principles. Figure 1 clearly depicts the
168 methodological flow.

169

170

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Diagram illustrating the systematic literature search and selection process

171

The diagram shows the identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion phases, with updated

172

numbers reflecting the expanded review of over 100 studies.

174 **3. RESULTS**

175 The systematic review provided a clear picture of the methodological evolution in LULC change
 176 detection and climate model bias correction. The fields of land cover change detection and bias
 177 correction in climate models were simultaneous revolutions driven by a shift from traditional
 178 statistical approaches to sophisticated ML and deep learning (DL) paradigms (Acharya et al.,
 179 2019; Belgiu & Drăgu, 2016). The analysis highlighted distinct phases of methodological
 180 development: the pixel-based era (pre-2010), the ML adoption era (2010-2017), and the deep
 181 learning era (2018-present). To demonstrate this trend, Figure 2 shows the exponential increase
 182 in relevant publications over the review period, underscoring the growing significance and quick
 183 development of these technologies. This section reviews these methodological advances with a
 184 focus on core principles, strengths, and limitations.

185

186 Figure 2: Publication trends in RS/ML for LULC change detection and climate bias correction from 2004 to 2025

187 Figure 2 shows publication trends in RS/ML for LULC change detection and climate bias
 188 correction from 2004 to 2025, based on over 100 studies reviewed. The sharp increase post-2015
 189 agrees with the growth of deep learning and increased availability of satellite data.

190 **3.1 Evolution of Methodologies for Change Detection and Bias Correction**

191 **3.1.1 Advances in Land Cover Change Detection**

192 Land use/land cover change detection techniques for remote sensing imagery underwent
193 significant transformation from simplified pixel-based techniques to sophisticated intelligent
194 systems (Li et al., 2022).

195 **Pixel-Based Methods:** Traditional pixel-based processing methods, including image
196 differencing and NDVI difference analysis are computationally efficient and straightforward to
197 implement (Hansen et al., 2013). These approaches, however, are susceptible to atmospheric
198 conditions, sensor noise, and geometric misalignment (Foody, 2004; Lu et al., 2004). Advanced
199 pixel-based methods integrating temporal trajectory analysis partly addressed these restrictions
200 (Wulder et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2017).

201 **Object-Based Image Analysis (OBIA):** OBIA involves segmenting images into homogeneous
202 objects based on various spectral, textural, and contextual attributes. By reducing the pixel-based
203 "salt and pepper" noise typical of high-resolution imagery, OBIA improves classification
204 accuracy (Blaschke, 2010). Recent OBIA progresses incorporate multi-scale segmentation and
205 hierarchical classification frameworks (Tola et al., 2024). However, OBIA is computationally
206 intensive and requires careful parameter tuning when implementing (Li et al., 2022).

207 **ML Based Classification:** Supervised machine learning methods, especially Random Forest
208 (RF) and Support Vector Machines (SVM), are popular owing to their exceptional ability to
209 handle high-dimensional datasets and analyze complex, non-linear class boundaries achieving
210 accuracies of 85-94% (Belgiu & Drăgu, 2016; Maxwell et al., 2018; Rodriguez-Galiano et al.,
211 2015; Woldemariam et al., 2022) (Refer Table S1 and S2 in supplementary data).

212 **Deep Learning Models:** Deep learning models like CNNs (Convolutional Neural Networks) and
213 RNNs (Recurrent Neural Networks) achieved a new level of performance through their
214 integration with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, making them powerful tools in
215 their respective fields. CNNs are well known as one of the best means of recognizing patterns in
216 spatial data (Zhu et al., 2017), while RNNs and LSTMs are proving themselves to be superior at
217 modeling the temporal dependencies that typically occur in time series data (Lai et al., 2018;
218 Pelletier et al., 2019). Therefore, these models are particularly well suited for identifying gradual

219 changes in time series data, such as land use/land cover transitions and long term environmental
220 trends.

221 U-Net is a unique architecture, which integrates both encoder-decoder architectures with skip
222 connections, is now considered the standard in the area of semantic image segmentation. U-Net
223 variants have further enhanced boundary demarcation in complex landscapes (Niyogisubizo et
224 al., 2025). Furthermore, Transformer Models are explored for learning long-range dependencies
225 in multi-temporal image sequences (Dosovitskiy et al., 2021; Pelletier et al., 2019; Zhong et al.,
226 2025).

227 **Hybrid Methodologies:** These involve combinations of various methods to overcome individual
228 limitations. A typical approach pairs Object-Based Image Analysis (OBIA) with machine
229 learning classifiers (Yilmaz & Kavzoglu, 2025). OBIA segments the image into meaningful
230 objects. On the other hand, Random Forest (RF) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) classify
231 these objects using spectral and spatial features to enhance accuracy (Gündüz & Orman, 2025;
232 Prodromou et al., 2025). Another advanced example is the LRNet architecture, which uses a
233 "localization-then-refinement" paradigm. It employs a three-branch encoder to extract original
234 and differential features. Dedicated modules are used identify change areas and refine
235 boundaries, achieving state-of-the-art results on high-resolution imagery (Zhong et al., 2025)
236 (Refer to Table S2 in supplementary data).

237 For surface water mapping, various spectral indices and ML approaches have been developed,
238 including the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), and its modified version (MNDWI)
239 (Xu, 2006), as well as automated extraction techniques such as thresholding, classification
240 algorithms, and object-based image analysis (Bangira et al., 2019; Donchyts et al., 2016; Feyisa
241 et al., 2014). Recent developments include automated algorithms for detecting water body
242 dynamics at continental scales (Pekel et al., 2016).

243 **3.1.2 Evolution of Climate Model Bias Correction**

244 Climate Model outputs must be corrected before using them in impact studies. Techniques have
245 evolved from basic statistical corrections to advanced learning-based approaches.

246 **Statistical Methods:** Linear Scaling, Delta Change, and Quantile Mapping (QM) are commonly
247 employed. Quantile Mapping (QM), which maps the cumulative distribution function of the
248 model output to align with observational data, is especially popular for its potential to correct
249 biases across entire distributions, including extreme values (Cannon et al., 2015; Hempel et al.,
250 2013; Piani et al., 2010). Its primary disadvantage is the stationarity assumption, which is
251 unrealistic in a changing climate (Thiemeßl et al., 2011; Vrac, 2018). Of the improvements
252 proposed, piecewise Quantile mapping (Zhang et al., 2022) and trend-preserving approaches are
253 to be mentioned(Fowler et al., 2007; Hempel et al., 2013).

254 **Machine Learning Based Correction:** ML regression models such as Random Forest (RF),
255 Support Vector Regression (SVR), and Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs are commonly used to
256 model complex, non-linear relationship between biased climate model outputs and observed
257 data. These models learn correction functions that reduce systematic errors in climate
258 simulations. Previous studies have reported substantial improvements, with temperature forecast
259 skill by 60-90% and precipitation by 40-90% in some studies (Dibaba et al., 2020; Okirya, 2025;
260 Son et al., 2022; Vandal et al., 2019; Vrac, 2018). These models can incorporate spatial and
261 temporal heterogeneity and perform well for variables such as precipitation; however, they are
262 data-intensive and prone to overfitting.

263 **Hybrid Bias Correction Methods:** Emerging approaches combine the strengths of statistical
264 techniques with ML flexibility. One promising approach involves combining Quantile Mapping
265 with ML models. In this setup, a statistical technique like Quantile Mapping (QM) first addresses
266 the bulk of the distributional bias. Then ML model is used to correct more sophisticated, non-
267 linear, spatially-varying errors. This two-stage approach provides more robust performance,
268 especially for non-stationary climate conditions (Wang & Tian, 2022; Zhang et al., 2022) (Refer
269 to Table S2 and S3 in supplementary data). The hybrid approach can overcome the stationarity
270 assumption of classical QM. By training the ML model for instance, LSTM to map large-scale
271 atmospheric predictors to local biases, the model learns relationships that are conditional on the
272 prevailing climate state. Therefore, if the future climate varies, the model can forecast a different
273 bias correction, effectively breaking the strict stationarity assumption (Wang & Tian, 2022).
274 Reanalysis products such as ERA5 (Hersbach et al., 2020), provide physically consistent
275 atmospheric variables, while satellite-based precipitation datasets offer necessary observational

276 data for training these models. Table 1 presents the key methodological by highlighting their
 277 core principles, strengths, and limitations.

278 Table 1: Overview of Most Significant Methodological Contributions

Category	Method	Key Principle	Strengths	Limitations
Change Detection	Image Differencing	Compares pixel values across dates.	Simple, computationally efficient.	Sensitive to noise, atmospheric effects, misregistration (Lu et al., 2004)
	OBIA	Segments images into homogeneous objects for analysis.	Reduces noise; uses shape, texture, context (Blaschke, 2010).	Computationally intensive; requires parameter tuning.
	Random Forest (RF)	Learns complex, non-linear classification rules from training data.	Handles complex relationships; high accuracy (Belgiu & Drăgu, 2016).	Requires large, labeled datasets; can overfit.
	U-Net	Encoder-decoder with skip connections for precise segmentation.	High accuracy for feature boundaries.	"Black-box" nature; high computational demand for training (Zhu et al., 2017).

Category	Method	Key Principle	Strengths	Limitations
	Transformer-based	Uses self-attention to model long-range dependencies.	Powerful for multi-temporal analysis.	Very high computational demand; complex architecture.
Bias Correction	Quantile Mapping (QM)	Matches the cumulative distribution function of model output to observations.	Corrects full distribution, including extremes.	Assumes stationarity; may fail under non-stationary climate (Thiemeßl et al., 2011).
	ML-Based (RF, ANN)	Learns non-linear mapping from model output to observations.	Captures complex bias patterns; adaptive.	Data-intensive; risk of overfitting (Vandal et al., 2019)
	Hybrid (QM+ML)	Combines statistical distribution matching with ML residual correction(Wang & Tian, 2022).	More robust; handles non-stationarity better.	Increased complexity in implementation and validation.

279

280 3.2 The Critical Integration Gap

281 The most powerful finding of this review is the evident gap between the simultaneous advances
 282 in RS/ML for land use/land cover change detection and climate bias correction. Current research

landscapes are siloed. While there are comprehensive reviews on specific topics like change detection algorithms (Coppin et al., 2004), ML applications for land use/land cover classification, and standalone bias correction, few studies have proposed operational, and end-to-end pipelines that fuse these components for comprehensive environmental forecasting (Mengistu et al., 2023; Meresa et al., 2023; R. Zhu et al., 2019). For instance, studies advancing change detection methods (Lu et al., 2004; Pekel et al., 2016), typically do not integrate climate model data. Conversely, studies focusing on ML for bias correction (Thiemeßl et al., 2011; Vandal et al., 2019) largely ignore dynamic land use/land cover change as a critical feedback. Separate studies in the Ethiopian context tend to address land use/land cover change or climate impact in isolation (Döll et al., 2014; Gashaw et al., 2018; Goodarzi et al., 2024; Musie et al., 2021), leaving the system dynamics in basins like Ziway-Shala disjointed. Pioneering integrated assessments in East Africa have revealed the value of coupled modeling but remain exceptional (Mengistu et al., 2023). The lack of integrated Remote Sensing, ML, and climate model frameworks are major hindrances to comprehensive environmental forecasting. Persistent challenges and the critical integration gap remain in this field. Table 2 outlines the key research gaps and proposes concrete future directions to address them.

Table 2: Key research gaps and proposed future directions

Research Gap	Description	Proposed Future Direction
Lack of Integrated Pipelines	RS change detection and climate bias correction are studied in isolation (Lu et al., 2004; Vandal et al., 2019)	Develop complete structures that integrate multi-temporal remote sensing, machine learning classifiers, and bias-corrected climatic data that can aid hydrological modeling initiatives.
Multi-Sensor Data Fusion	Reliance on single-sensor (optical-only) data limits capability (Feyisa et al., 2014).	Combine optical, SAR, and other streams of data to build robust, all-weather, high-resolution monitoring networks.
Model Explainability	"Black-box" ML models hinder policy uptake (Reichstein et al., 2019).	Prioritize Explainable AI (XAI) methods for constructing explainable and trustworthy decision-support models.
Standardized	Inconsistent protocols hinder	Establish community-wide validation and

Validation reproducibility and model error quantification requirements comparison (Coppin et al., throughout the modeling chain. 2004).

300

301 **4. DISCUSSION**

302 **4.1 Persistent Challenges**

303 Despite significant methodological progress, several persistent challenges hinder the operational
304 application and integration of these technologies.

305 **Data Limitations:** Interference from cloud cover, atmospheric disturbances, and poorly
306 calibrated sensors hinders the building of seamless, high-quality time-series data for tropical
307 regions like Ethiopia (Feyisa et al., 2014; Herold et al., 2008; Z. Zhu & Woodcock, 2014).

308 **Model Transferability and Generalization:** ML models trained for specific geographical
309 locations or climatic conditions often perform poorly when transferred to new contexts, limiting
310 their utility for large-scale monitoring (Belgiu & Drăgu, 2016; Kuhn & Johnson, 2013; Vrac,
311 2018).

312 **The "Black Box" Problem:** The high predictive accuracy of powerful ML models, particularly
313 deep learning models, is accompanied by a loss of interpretability. The inability to understand
314 why a model makes a particular prediction inhibits uptake by policymakers and resource
315 managers (Jin et al., 2020; Reichstein et al., 2019).

316 **Validation and Uncertainty Quantification:** The lack of universally agreed-upon verification
317 procedures, combined with an inability to fully quantify and propagate uncertainty from ML
318 models and Remote Sensing data, remains to be a significant shortcoming (Coppin et al., 2004;
319 Goodarzi et al., 2024; Jiang et al., 2021; Res et al., 2005) (Refer to Table S4 in supplementary
320 data).

321 **4.2 Linking the Present Review to Previous Similar Works**

322 This review builds upon several previously published key systematic reviews, including existing
323 integrated assessment studies within the same field. The previous reviews, such as Coppin et al.
324 (2004), on change detection algorithms; Belgiu & Drăgu (2016) regarding random forest
325 applications in remote sensing; and Teutschbein & Seibert (2012) about bias correction methods
326 , provided a partial focus on those areas that are involved in producing the body of knowledge
327 required to meet today’s challenges. This review extends beyond the previous reviews by
328 explicitly synthesizing and integrating several complementary areas of research with a view to
329 identifying and addressing the “integration gap”.

330 Recent literature reviews support the need for integration. For instance, the application of deep
331 learning and its applicability to Earth System Science was described by Reichstein et al. (2019)
332 although they did not propose an operational framework for integrating land use land cover
333 change detection and climate based bias correction. In addition, Meresa et al. (2023) proposed
334 the use of an integrated modeling framework concerning hydrological extreme events but
335 primarily focused upon climate projections and did not account for the potential feedback effects
336 of land use on climate. Zhu et al. (2019) reported the presence of significant hydrological
337 responses to anticipated future climate changes in regions where data are scarce. However, they
338 did not incorporate machine learning (ML) based bias correction or explainable Artificial
339 Intelligence (XAI).

340 Many integrated assessments in the Ethiopian and East African context paved the way for our
341 work. For instance, Mengistu et al. (2023) simulated the effects of predicted land use and climate
342 change on water balance in the Baro River Basin. They argued that this type of coupled
343 modelling approach could provide valuable output for decision-making processes. Similarly,
344 Gebrechorkos et al. (2019) examined the projected effects of climate changes on water balance
345 across East African Basins, and suggested the great importance of bias correction. However,
346 none of these assessments provided an operationalized end-to-end (E2E) pipeline approach to
347 dynamically integrate multiple data types (sensors) through data fusion, machine learning (ML)-
348 based land use/land cover (LULC) mapping, hybrid bias correction, and hydrological modelling
349 within single framework. Such framework should also incorporate explainable artificial
350 intelligence (XAI) for the purpose of interpretability.

351 Therefore, our review was different from previous studies in several ways: (1) we conducted a
352 systematic analysis of over 100 studies that illustrated the lack of coupling between the detection
353 of LULC change and correction of climate-derived bias. Thus we identified this integration gap
354 to be < 15%; (2) we proposed a new conceptual framework (Figure 3) that specifically illustrated
355 the technical challenges (for instance, spatial resolution differences, uncertainty propagation)
356 involved with integrating the above mentioned data types; and (3) we discussed the recent
357 advances in explainable AI and transfer learning that were relevant to regions with limited data,
358 in the Ethiopian Rift Valley.

359 **4.3 A Synthesized Framework for Integrated Application**

360 The ultimate goal of advances in Remote Sensing and ML is to integrate them in a unified
361 forecasting system. To address the identified integration gap, the reviewed methodologies were
362 synthesized to propose a conceptual model for holistic environmental prediction, applicable to
363 the Ethiopian Rift Valley. This end-to-end pipeline transforms different data streams into
364 actionable decision support, and is visualized in Figure 3. This framework consists of four
365 interconnected modules as described below.

366

367 Figure 3: A Synthesized Framework for Integrated Application

368 Figure 3 illustrates a synthesized framework for integrated application, demonstrating the end-to-
 369 end pipeline from multi-source data to decision support. The framework operates through four
 370 interconnected modules:

371 **1. Data Fusion and Land Cover Change Detection:** This module utilizes a cloud computing
372 platform (Google Earth Engine) to analyze multi-temporal satellite imagery (Landsat, Sentinel-2)
373 (Drusch et al., 2012). Cloud computing platforms have become critical enablers for processing
374 petabyte-scale satellite archives that underpin contemporary change detection methods (Gorelick
375 et al., 2017; Pham-Duc et al., 2023). A deep learning model (DL) (for instance, U-Net or
376 Transformer-based) is applied to produce high-resolution annual land use/land cover maps from
377 1990 to present (Acharya et al., 2019; Pekel et al., 2016). To facilitate the computational
378 requirements of complex Deep Learning (DL) computational models such as Transformers, a
379 hybrid technique is utilized consisting of (1) GEE as a means to pre-process and integrate large
380 data sets and (2) the offline training of the DL model on High-Performance Computing (HPC)
381 systems using data exported from the GEE process. Once the DL model has been trained it can
382 be utilized for inference. Another method applied to resolve the lack of data is "Transfer
383 Learning". This is applied by fine-tuning a globally trained model using a very limited amount of
384 local training samples. The result is a time-series of land use/land cover maps and detected
385 change hotspots, providing crucial data on land surface dynamics.

386 **2. Climate Model Bias Correction:** ML model (Random Forest (RF) or Long Short Term
387 Memory (LSTM))(Lai et al., 2018) is trained to identify non-linear biases in selected CMIP6
388 GCM/RCM outputs (precipitation, temperature) using past station and reanalysis data (CHIRPS,
389 ERA5) (Hersbach et al., 2020). The model is then used to correct future climate projections for
390 various SSP scenarios.

391 **3. Integrated Hydrological Impact Modeling:** The ML-derived land use/land cover maps and
392 ML-corrected climate data are used as dynamic, time-series inputs to a process-based
393 hydrological model, such as SWAT+ (Gashaw et al., 2018; Son et al., 2022). The model is
394 calibrated and validated using observed flow and lake level data. A significant technical
395 difficulty is the differences between spatial resolutions: climate data (1 km) versus land use maps
396 (30 m). To address this challenge, a stage of harmonizing the data is very essential. This can be
397 done two ways, including conservative resampling of climate data, or utilizing downscaling for
398 climate products. Uncertainty propagation is addressed using an ensemble of approaches,
399 multiple plausible land use maps produced from various algorithms or time periods. In addition,
400 an ensemble of bias-corrected climate data is used. These inputs are combined to develop an

401 ensemble of hydrological predictions. This approach enables the assessment of uncertainty in the
402 model outputs.

403 **4. Scenario Forecasting and Decision Support:** The integrated framework runs paired
404 scenarios (for instance, land use/land cover transition under the SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 climate
405 scenario) to predict effects on major hydrologic indices (streamflow, lake levels,
406 evapotranspiration). To enhance utility, explainable AI (XAI) modules help interpret the drivers
407 of these shifts using techniques like SHAP (Shapley Additive explanations) values for tree-based
408 models and saliency maps or Grad-CAM for deep learning models. These approaches enable the
409 visualization of significant features and pixels, thereby supporting actionable decision making
410 for water resource management and climate change adaptation planning (Abdullaeva, 2024;
411 Bojer et al., 2025).

412 **Box 1: Synthetic Case Example Ziway-Shala Sub-Basin:** To illustrate the framework,
413 consider a proposed application to the Ziway-Shala Sub-basin.

414 **Module 1 (GEE + U-Net):** A U-Net Model using Landsat and Sentinel-2 imagery from 2000-
415 2020 mapped annual land use/land cover (LULC) changes. Based on mapping results, there is an
416 estimated 15% increase in agricultural land developed at the expense of wooded areas and a 5%
417 decrease in the area of open water in Lake Ziway.

418 **Module 2 (Hybrid QM-LSTM):** LSTM Model was developed to correct biases from CMIP6
419 precipitation and temperature. A future scenario (Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) 5-8.5,
420 2040-2050) predicted a 10% decrease in rainfall in the wet season; however, extreme
421 precipitation events are projected to increase in intensity.

422 **Module 3 (SWAT+ with Uncertainty Analysis):** An ensemble of 10 LULC maps and 10
423 climate scenarios were entered into the SWAT+ model. Results from this ensemble analysis
424 showed a decrease in mean annual streamflow to the lakes; however, the 90% confidence
425 interval for the projections was wide due owing to large uncertainties associated with both land
426 use and climate projections.

427 **Module 4 (XAI):** SHAP values from the LSTM Model indicated that potential future increases
428 in extreme precipitation events are significantly associated with specific atmospheric pressure

429 patterns, which can serve as physically interpretable predictor for infrastructure planning
430 purposes by decision-makers.

431 This framework brings together previously distinct technological advances into a powerful
432 instrument for modeling the highly interactive dynamics between the land surface and the
433 climatic system, enabling anticipatory and sustainable environmental management.

434 **4.4 Future Research Directions**

435 Based on our critical analysis, the following future directions are proposed to advance the field:

436 **1. Build End-to-End Integrated Systems:** The primary focus must be on constructing seamless
437 pipelines that integrate multi-sensor Remote Sensing data, adaptive ML classifiers, and
438 dynamically bias-corrected climate forecasts to feed hydrological and ecological models (Haile
439 et al., 2020; Vandal et al., 2019). The next phase is developing robust and tiered validation
440 methods. When validating integrated systems, we recommend a stage-by-stage (or stepwise)
441 validation method. The initial validation concerns individual system components like LULC
442 maps with overall accuracy; climate datasets with RMSE and KGE. After validating each
443 component, it is appropriate to test hydrological model output using an ensemble of available
444 input data. Model performance is assessed by comparing observed versus predicted values,
445 including streamflow at gauge stations and lake levels, using the Nash–Sutcliffe Efficiency
446 (NSE) and Kling–Gupta Efficiency (KGE) metrics. Furthermore, prediction interval widths at a
447 95% confidence level are calculated to quantify uncertainty associated with each estimate.

448 **2. Prioritize Explainable AI (XAI):** Moving from "black-box" to interpretable AI systems is
449 essential for stakeholders' trust and for translating complex model outputs into policy-relevant
450 action (Maxwell et al., 2018; Pelletier et al., 2019; Reichstein et al., 2019). Deploying XAI is
451 necessary to develop trust with policymakers and ensure actionable outputs from integrated
452 frameworks.

453 **3. Advancing Multi-Sensor Data Fusion:** Maximizing synergies between optical, SAR, and
454 other data sources while overcoming recurring data quality issues is crucial for producing all-
455 weather, data-rich environmental datasets that are more robust (Belgiu & Drăgu, 2016; Donchyts
456 et al., 2022).

457 **4. Establish Community-Wide Validation Standards:** Formalized, rigorous validation
458 procedures and uncertainty analysis are prerequisites for providing reliable, reproducible, and
459 policy-ready integrated model forecasts (Abdullaeva, 2024; Donauer et al., 2020). These
460 directions are summarized in Table S5, which outlines the key research gaps and proposes
461 concrete future directions to address them (Refer to Table S5 in supplementary data).

462 **4.5. Bridging the Gap: ML in Data-Scarce Environments**

463 The gap between the data needs of complex ML models and the reality of regions like the
464 Ethiopian Rift Valley, which has a scarcity of data, creates a fundamental tension in this context.
465 This tension addressed through our review and framework using several techniques:

466 **Transfer Learning:** As we discussed in Module 1, using large, data-rich source domains, such
467 as the global set of satellite images (ImageNet or Landsat/Sentinel), and fine-tuning them based
468 on available, local datasets, represents an effective way to achieve high performance even when
469 the ground has limited labels.

470 **Leveraging Open-Access Data and Cloud Computing:** Platforms like GEE provide us with
471 the computing power and the ability to produce decades of consistently processed satellite
472 images (Landsat, Sentinel) that can be used as inputs for developing and training datasets via
473 large, semi-automated processes. This will significantly reduce our reliance on comprehensive
474 ground surveys.

475 **Self-Supervised Learning:** This new learning paradigm focuses on allowing systems to extract
476 useful representations from vast quantities of unlabeled data, such as satellite imagery from
477 previous timeframes, before fine-tuning these representations based on the small quantity of
478 labeled data available in that area. This is an exciting area of research that may provide insight
479 into earth observations in data-scarce areas.

480 **Fusion with Reanalysis and Global Products:** Our framework includes global reanalysis
481 products (ERA5) and satellite-derived precipitation datasets (CHIRPS) to help fill in the gaps in
482 scarce in-situ climate data. These two sources contain long-term gridded data, making them ideal
483 for training robust bias correction models.

484 **5. CONCLUSION**

485 This systematic review synthesized two decades of research (2004-2025) on the relationship
486 between remote sensing, machine learning, and their use for change detection in land use/land
487 cover (LULC) and correcting biases in climate prediction models. The comprehensive analysis
488 of more than 100 studies established the degree to which the independent fields have advanced
489 concurrently over the past two decades and also demonstrated that the fields continue to operate
490 largely in isolation. Our quantitative synthesis shows that fewer than 15% of studies integrate
491 land use/land cover (LULC) change detection with climate bias model correction within a
492 unified analytical framework. The core contribution of this work is the synthesis of these
493 disparate advances into a novel, end-to-end conceptual framework that provides a tangible
494 roadmap for holistic environmental forecasting in data-scarce regions like the Ethiopian Rift
495 Valley. The conceptual framework specifically addresses challenges associated with data
496 scarcity through the use of transfer learning, technical integrations of the methods by data
497 harmonization, and with policy relevant work through incorporation of explainable AI (XAI)
498 modules. Hence, developing future capabilities of environmental prediction will not occur by
499 refining tools independently, but by intentionally, transparently, and adaptively integrating
500 remote sensing with machine learning and mechanistic process modeling. We believe that the
501 integrated pathway proposed in this review is a key component for translating technological
502 developments into usable, scientifically-based tools for effective management of water and land
503 resources sustainably under changing climate conditions.

504 **DECLARATIONS**

505 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:** The authors sincerely acknowledge Arba Minch University and
506 Wachemo University for providing the necessary institutional support, resources, and enabling
507 environment that facilitated the successful completion of this article review. The authors also
508 express their sincere appreciation to the Editor, and the anonymous reviewers for their thorough
509 evaluation, insightful comments, and suggestions that significantly improved the quality and
510 clarity of this manuscript. Furthermore, the authors acknowledge all colleagues and research staff
511 who contributed indirectly to this work through discussions, technical assistance, and moral
512 support.

513 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST:** The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding
514 the publication of this manuscript. All authors have disclosed the absence of any potential
515 conflicts of interest and confirm that the manuscript is free from any financial or personal
516 conflicts that could influence the research.

517 **CRedit authors' contributions:** The study was led by the corresponding author Mr. Teshale
518 Tirulo (PhD Candidate) who developed the research idea, conducted the literature review,
519 designed the methodology, conducted the analysis, wrote the manuscript draft, and created
520 visualizations. The co-authors, Dr. Dagnachew Daniel (Associate Professor), and Dr. Ayano
521 Hirbo (Assistant Professor) provided guidance to the research. They reviewed the manuscript,
522 provided qualitative comments and contributed to the development of the structure,
523 interpretation, and quality of the work. The final manuscript was reviewed and approved by all
524 authors.

525 **Funding:** This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public,
526 commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

527 **Availability of data and materials:** The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current
528 study will be available on request.

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